

1 **Community Detection Reveals Multiple Rich Cores in Indonesia's**

2 **Intranational Production Network**

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8

9 **Abstract**

10 This study examines the mesoscale organization of Indonesia's intranational production
11 network using the 2016 Interregional Input–Output (IRIO) table. We represent intermediate
12 transactions as a weighted, directed supra-network of 578 province–sector nodes and combine
13 three network tools in a single pipeline, namely consensus Leiden community detection,
14 weighted rich-club analysis, and inter-community minimum-spanning-tree (MST) backbone
15 extraction. We evaluate whether production communities are primarily geographic or
16 functional, measure how economically central rich province–sector nodes concentrate across
17 communities using enrichment tests, and interpret what the inter-community backbone implies
18 for national integration. Results show that communities are predominantly geographic, aligning
19 strongly with provinces and island groupings rather than sector labels, and thus forming
20 spatially cohesive but multi-sector production clusters. Despite weak specialization by sector
21 labels, communities remain functionally differentiated in their value-added and external-
22 strength sector profiles. In many communities, the leading sectors that generate value added
23 are not the same as those that mediate cross-community exchange. Rich-club and enrichment

24 analyses show that rich nodes are concentrated in a small number of rich-core communities,
25 indicating a multi-core organizational structure. Java-centered communities dominate the
26 national rich core, while selected communities outside Java, particularly in Sumatra, occupy
27 intermediate positions within the multi-core hierarchy. The inter-community MST reveals a
28 Java-centered corridor connecting western, central, and eastern Indonesia through two strategic
29 hubs. Jakarta serves as an intermediation center, and East Java functions as an industrial and
30 logistical hub. The backbone also highlights potential bottlenecks associated with corridor
31 dependence. Overall, the mesoscale framework provides a systematic basis to understand how
32 functional production communities and key interregional corridors jointly shape the structure
33 of Indonesia's production network, with implications for spatial inequality and systemic
34 resilience.

35 **Keywords:** Indonesia Interregional Input–Output Table, Production Network, Input-Output
36 Network, Rich Community, Multicore Organization.

37

38 **1. Introduction**

39 Understanding the structure of national production systems is essential for explaining how
40 economies respond to shocks and how regional imbalances develop and persist. Production
41 linkages between regions and sectors determine both economic resilience to shocks and the
42 spatial distribution of value (Acemoglu et al. 2012; Carvalho 2014). In economies with diverse
43 spatial characteristics, the configuration of interregional production dependencies can either
44 buffer the system by dispersing shocks through multiple pathways (Gomez et al. 2020;
45 Giannakis et al. 2024) or reinforce core–periphery–type structures that concentrate high-value
46 activities in a small core and reproduce structural inequality across regions (Kostoska et al.

47 2020). Identifying this structure is therefore crucial for assessing vulnerabilities and
48 understanding the spatial dimensions of national development (Hidalgo and Hausmann 2009).
49 Conventional input–output (IO) analysis, pioneered by Leontief (1936, 1941), established a
50 systematic methodology for tracking the flow of goods and services between sectors within an
51 economy. This approach was later expanded to regional and interregional levels, allowing
52 researchers to examine how spatial and sectoral linkages influence national development (Isard
53 1951; Miller and Blair 2009). Recent developments have reconceptualized IO systems as
54 complex networks, where industries or region–sector pairs are visualized as nodes, connected
55 by weighted, directed links that depict intermediate transactions (McNerney et al. 2013; Cerina
56 et al. 2015; Xu and Liang 2019). The network perspective integrates economic and complex
57 systems theory, enabling analysis of interdependence, centrality, and clustering within
58 production networks. By revealing the structure of inter-industry connections, network-based
59 IO research offers a greater understanding of shock propagation, value creation, and systemic
60 vulnerabilities in modern economies (Acemoglu et al. 2012; Battiston et al. 2012; Los et al.
61 2014).

62 Network analysis of multi-regional input–output (MRIO) data has significantly advanced our
63 understanding of the structural organization of production. At the global level, studies of the
64 World Input–Output Database (WIOD) reveal that international production forms a highly
65 organized, multilayer network. Research shows that industries and countries cluster into
66 modular communities and hierarchical cores, reflecting the continental structure of global value
67 creation (Cerina et al. 2015; del Río-Chanona et al. 2017; Piccardi et al. 2017). Further studies
68 have measured the diversity and strength of inter-industry linkages using entropy and
69 multilayer metrics (Alves et al. 2018) and evaluated the robustness and rankings of global
70 production communities (Kireyev et al. 2022). Recent findings highlight that the global IO
71 system exhibits strong hierarchical sectoral connections and persistent spatial modularity

72 (Soyyigit and Boz 2017; Bartesaghi et al. 2022), indicating that the global production network
73 is organized with dense regional cores and overlapping sectoral communities.

74 In comparison, relatively few studies have examined intranational MRIO production networks
75 from a network-science perspective. For China, network analysis of provincial MRIO tables
76 has identified growth-driving province–sector clusters using community detection, showing
77 that community structure aligns closely with geography and that regional fragmentation has
78 intensified over time (Wang et al. 2021). For the United States, multilayer models of
79 intranational MRIO production networks highlight the importance of cross-sector coupling.
80 Interlayer connections can amplify shock propagation, and cascade simulations indicate that
81 cross-sector dependence increases systemic fragility and regional vulnerability (Gomez et al.
82 2020). Our previous study of Indonesia’s intranational production network documented a
83 hierarchical core–periphery structure in the 2016 IRIO system, in which economically
84 dominant province–sector nodes maintain extensive links with peripheral nodes (Maulana et
85 al. 2024). Collectively, these national studies suggest that a network perspective can reveal
86 functional production communities and key interregional corridors, helping clarify how
87 regional specialization co-evolves with interdependence.

88 This study investigates the mesoscale organization of Indonesia’s intranational production
89 network. As a large archipelagic nation, Indonesia’s regional production systems are
90 geographically dispersed yet increasingly interconnected through interprovincial trade
91 (Statistics Indonesia (BPS) 2025). At the same time, uneven development patterns across
92 islands (Akita and Kataoka 2023) raise important questions about how production linkages
93 across locations and sectors are structured and how connectivity may shape both integration
94 and concentration. Extending our previous research, this study examines the organization of
95 economically central (rich) province–sector nodes, asking whether Indonesia’s production
96 system is characterized by a single dominant community that concentrates rich nodes or by a

97 multicore configuration of multiple interlinked rich communities connected through bridging
98 regions and sectors (Rombach et al. 2017; Yan and Luo 2019). Using the 2016 Interregional
99 Input–Output (IRIO) table, we model the economy as a weighted, directed network of
100 province–sector nodes linked by intermediate transactions. We then apply the Leiden algorithm
101 for community detection (Traag et al. 2019), weighted rich-club analysis (Alstott et al. 2014),
102 and minimum-spanning-tree (MST) backbone extraction (Kruskal 1956) to identify cohesive
103 production communities, locate rich nodes, and map the primary inter-community trade
104 corridors. This framework provides a systematic basis for interpreting how functional
105 production communities and key interregional corridors jointly shape the structure of
106 Indonesia’s production network, with implications for spatial inequality and systemic
107 resilience.

108 This paper makes three contributions. First, we construct a province–sector IRIO production
109 network for Indonesia (2016) and provide a mesoscale characterization that integrates
110 consensus Leiden community detection, weighted rich-club identification, and backbone
111 extraction within a single analytical pipeline. Second, we move beyond node-level centrality
112 by identifying rich-core communities, defined as communities with statistically significant
113 over-representation of rich province–sector nodes, enabling a community-level test of whether
114 economic centrality is organized as a single core or a polycentric set of core communities.
115 Third, we derive an inter-community backbone to map the principal corridors sustaining
116 national production integration and to identify potential structural bottlenecks with
117 implications for spatial inequality and systemic resilience.

118 The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the data and methods,
119 including the construction of the IRIO network and the application of community, rich-club,
120 and backbone analyses. Section 3 presents the results, emphasizing the community structures,
121 rich-node concentrations, and inter-community backbone patterns that characterize Indonesia’s

122 production network. Section 4 discusses the economic implications of these patterns, especially
 123 concerning spatial inequality and systemic resilience. Section 5 summarizes the key findings.

124 **2. Data and Method**

125 2.1 Data

126 In this study, we use the 2016 Indonesian Interregional Input–Output (IRIO) table, which was
 127 prepared by Statistics Indonesia (Statistics Indonesia (BPS) 2021). Figure 1 shows the
 128 schematic of the IRIO table. We focus on the intermediate supply-demand (I) matrix that
 129 details how different industries trade goods and services with each other across 34 provinces
 130 and 17 sectors. Each cell in the matrix shows the monetary value of goods and services sent
 131 from one province and sector to another, recorded in millions of Indonesian Rupiah at basic
 132 prices.

			Intermediate Use						Final Demand	Total Output
			Province 1			Province N				
			Sector 1	...	Sector k	Sector 1	...	Sector k		
Intermediate Input	Province 1	Sector 1	I						II	IV
		...								
		Sector k								
	Province N	Sector 1								
		...								
		Sector k								
Import			III							
Value Added										
Total Input			IV							

133
 134 *Figure 1 Schematic structure of the 2016 Indonesian interregional input–output (IRIO) system. The intermediate transaction*
 135 *block records interprovincial inter-industry flows; final demand and value-added accounts complete the IO identity linking*
 136 *intermediate use (I), final demand (II), value added (III) and total output/input (IV). Data source: BPS (2021)*

137 Besides intermediate transactions, we use the value-added accounts from the same IRIO system
 138 to describe the economic size of each province-sector and summarize value added at higher
 139 levels in later comparisons. The full lists of the 17 sectors and the broader 5-sector

140 classification, along with the 34 provinces and the 7-island grouping, are available in Appendix
 141 A Tables 7-8 for reference.

142 2.2 Supra-adjacency representation and graph definition

143 We represent the IRIO intermediate transaction block as a single weighted, directed network
 144 over province–sector accounts (McNerney et al. 2013; Xu & Liang 2019). Let $\alpha, \beta \in \{1, \dots, k\}$
 145 index sectors with $k=17$ and let $i, j \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ index provinces with $N = 34$. Each province–
 146 sector account is treated as a node (i, α) , giving a total of $N \times K = 578$ nodes.

147 Let $Z^{\alpha, \beta} \in \mathbb{R}_+^{N \times N}$ denote the IRIO intermediate transaction block written in sector-by-sector
 148 submatrices, where $Z_{ij}^{\alpha\beta}$ is the monetary value of intermediate inputs supplied from province i
 149 in sector α to province j in sector β . We then construct the supra-adjacency matrix $W \in$
 150 $\mathbb{R}_+^{Nk \times Nk}$ as a $k \times k$ block matrix $W = [W^{\alpha\beta}]_{\alpha, \beta=1}^k$, with each block $W^{\alpha\beta} \in \mathbb{R}_+^{N \times N}$ defined
 151 elementwise by

$$152 \quad W_{ij}^{\alpha\beta} = \begin{cases} Z_{ij}^{\alpha\beta}, & \text{if an intermediate transaction from } (i, \alpha) \text{ to } (j, \beta) \text{ is recorded,} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

153 Equivalently, W defines a weighted, directed graph $G = (V, E, w)$ with node set $V =$
 154 $\{(i, \alpha): i = 1, \dots, N; \alpha = 1, \dots, k\}$ and edge set $E = \{((i, \alpha), (j, \beta)): W_{ij}^{\alpha\beta} > 0\}$, where the edge
 155 weight is $w_{(i, \alpha), (j, \beta)} = W_{ij}^{\alpha\beta}$. We set self-loops to zero, $W_{ii}^{\alpha\alpha} = 0$, so that the network structure
 156 reflects interdependence across distinct province–sector accounts rather than within-account
 157 flows. All analyses use the raw intermediate transaction flows from the IRIO table as edge
 158 weights, without additional normalization. This supra-adjacency representation is equivalent
 159 to flattening the sector-layered IRIO structure used in previous work (Bartesaghi et al. 2022;
 160 Maulana et al. 2024) into a single weighted, directed network over province–sector accounts.

161 2.3 Rich-club analysis

162 To assess whether high-strength province–sector nodes form a tightly interconnected core, we
 163 conduct a weighted rich-club analysis on the directed supra-network (Zhou and Mondragon
 164 2004; Alstott et al. 2014).

165 *Richness definitions and thresholds.* We define node richness under two complementary
 166 measures: (i) Seller size (node out-strength) : $r_i = s_i^{out} = \sum_j w_{ij}$, summarizing the total
 167 intermediate sales from province–sector i to the rest of the system; (ii) Buyer size (node in-
 168 strength): $r_i = s_i^{in} = \sum_j w_{ji}$, summarizing the total intermediate purchases by province–
 169 sector i . Nodes are ranked by the corresponding strength. We report results for the 90th, 95th,
 170 and 99th percentiles (top 10%, 5%, and 1% of nodes) and also treat richness as a continuous
 171 threshold to construct rich-club curves.

172 *Weighted rich-club intensity.* For a threshold r , let $R(r)$ denote the set of rich nodes and E_r the
 173 set of directed edges among them. We measure within-rich intensity using the weighted rich-
 174 club coefficient, as follows (Alstott et al. 2014):

$$175 \quad \phi^w(r) = \frac{\sum_{(i,j) \in E_r} w_{ij}}{\sum_{k=1}^{|E_r|} w_{(k)}^\downarrow} \quad (2)$$

176 where $w_{(k)}^\downarrow$ are all network edge weights sorted in descending order.

177 To test whether within-rich concentration exceeds what is expected under node-level strength
 178 constraints, we use a weight-reshuffling null on a fixed topology, generating 1,000 strength-
 179 preserving randomized control networks that keep the set of non-zero links unchanged while
 180 permuting weights across existing edges (Alstott et al. 2014). For seller-richness, we preserve
 181 each node’s out-strength s_i^{out} by permuting its outgoing weights across its outgoing links. For
 182 buyer-richness, we preserve each node’s in-strength s_i^{in} by permuting its incoming weights
 183 across its incoming links.

184 We report the normalized rich-club ratio as follows:

185
$$\rho^w(r) = \frac{\phi^w(r)}{\langle \phi_{rand}^w(r) \rangle} \quad (3)$$

186 where $\langle \cdot \rangle$ denotes the ensemble mean. Values $\rho^w(r) > 1$ indicate rich-club ordering, $\rho^w(r) \approx$
 187 1 consistency with the null, and $\rho^w(r) < 1$ outward-oriented mixing.

188 **2.4 Community detection and robustness**

189 We detect communities in the weighted, directed supra-network of Indonesian IRIO to
 190 characterize mesoscale modular structure and to relate modules to rich-club organization.

191 Our primary community detection method is the Leiden algorithm (Traag et al. 2019), applied
 192 to the weighted, directed graph $G = (V, E, w)$. For a partition C with labels $\{c_i\}$, we use
 193 directed, weighted modularity, as follows (Newman 2006; Leicht and Newman):

194
$$Q(C) = \frac{1}{W_{tot}} \sum_{i,j} \left[w_{ij} - \gamma \frac{s_i^{out} s_j^{in}}{W_{tot}} \right] 1\{c_i = c_j\} \quad (4)$$

195 where w_{ij} is the edge weight, $W_{tot} = \sum_{ij} w_{ij}$, γ is the resolution parameter (Reichardt and
 196 Bornholdt 2006), and $1\{.\}$ is the Kronecker indicator. We scan $\gamma \in \{0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0\}$,
 197 run the method 1000 times and obtain a single consensus partition via an agreement-matrix
 198 (co-assignment) consensus procedure (Appendix B).

199 As a robustness check, we apply InfoMap (Rosvall and Bergstrom 2008) to the same weighted,
 200 directed network. We compare InfoMap and Leiden partitions using partition-similarity
 201 measures, including normalized mutual information (NMI) and variation of information (VI)
 202 (Danon et al. 2005; Meilă 2007), to assess whether the main mesoscale patterns are stable
 203 across methods and across the Leiden resolution scan.

204 **2.5 Community network and backbone extraction**

205 To visualize mesoscale interdependence and summarize the dominant corridors of inter-
 206 community exchange, we construct a community network by aggregating flows between
 207 communities and then extract a sparse backbone using a minimum spanning tree (MST).

208 2.5.1 Community-to-community flows

209 Let c_i denote the community label of node i from the Leiden partition at $\gamma = 1.0$. We define
 210 the directed community–community flow matrix F as

$$211 F_{cd} = \sum_{i:c_i=c} \sum_{j:c_j=d} w_{ij} \quad (5)$$

212 which aggregates intermediate flows from community c to community d . We do not treat
 213 within-community flows F_{cc} as edges in the inter-community backbone. For backbone
 214 construction, we symmetrize inter-community flows into an undirected bilateral coupling
 215 weight as $S_{cd} = F_{cd} + F_{dc}$, ($c \neq d$), so that each undirected edge (c, d) represents the total
 216 two-way intermediate interdependence between communities c and d .

217 2.5.2 MST backbone

218 We construct an MST on the undirected weighted community network S_{cd} to obtain a
 219 connected and interpretable backbone of inter-community coupling (Kruskal 1956; Aste 2025).

220 We define edge “distance” as

$$221 l_{cd} = \frac{1}{S_{cd} + \varepsilon} \quad (6)$$

222 with $\varepsilon = 10^{-12}$ to avoid division by zero. MST is the tree T that minimizes $\sum_{(c,d) \in T} l_{cd}$, which
 223 is equivalent to maximizing $\sum_{(c,d) \in T} S_{cd}$ over tree edges. We use the resulting MST topology
 224 to describe the backbone structure of inter-community exchange and to support later
 225 interpretation of corridor, core, and peripheral communities.

226 2.6 Interpreting communities: geography, sectors, and rich nodes

227 2.6.1 Geography vs function

228 To evaluate whether detected communities are primarily geographic (province/island blocs) or
 229 functional (sector/value-chain clustering), we relate community assignments to exogenous
 230 labels for province, island, and sector (17 sectors and a coarser sector classification; see
 231 Appendix A Tables 7–8). We quantify alignment between the community partition and each
 232 labeling using normalized mutual information (NMI) and the adjusted Rand index (ARI)
 233 (Hubert and Arabie 1985; Meilă 2007). We complement these summary measures with
 234 descriptive visualizations, including heatmaps (community-by-province, community-by-
 235 island, community-by-sector) and maps of community assignment by province.

236 To characterize the economic and functional composition of each community, we aggregate
 237 node attributes by community C and five-sector classification s . The value-added profile is
 238 computed as $VA_{C,s} = \sum_{i \in (C,s)} VA_i$, and we report within-community shares $VA_{C,s} / \sum_s VA_{C,s}$.

239 To capture the community’s interface with the rest of the network, we compute external-only
 240 strength using cross-community flows: $S_{C,s}^{ext} = \sum_{i \in (C,s)} \sum_{j \notin C} (w_{i \rightarrow j} + w_{j \rightarrow i})$, and report within-
 241 community shares $S_{C,s}^{ext} / \sum_s S_{C,s}^{ext}$.

242 2.6.2 Rich-node enrichment and concentration across communities

243 To connect mesoscale community structure with rich-club organization, we classify nodes as
 244 rich using the thresholds in Section 2.3 and study their distribution across communities. For a
 245 given threshold, let K be the total number of rich nodes in the network and N the total number
 246 of nodes. For a community c with n_c nodes and k_c rich nodes, we define the rich-node
 247 enrichment index

$$248 E_c = \log_2 \left(\frac{k_c/n_c}{K/N} \right) \quad (7)$$

249 so that $E_c > 0$ indicates enrichment, $E_c = 0$ indicates no enrichment, and $E_c < 0$ indicates
 250 depletion. We assess statistical significance using a hypergeometric label-randomization null
 251 model that preserves K (Rivals et al. 2006), compute one-sided enrichment p-values $p_c =$

252 $P(K_c \geq k_c)$, and adjust for multiple testing across communities using the Benjamini–Hochberg
 253 false discovery rate (FDR) procedure (Benjamini and Hochberg 1995) (Appendix C). We
 254 classify a community as a rich-core community if it exhibits over-representation of rich nodes,
 255 i.e., $E_c > 0$ and the FDR-adjusted p_c is significant at conventional levels (*** $p < 0.001$, **
 256 $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$). For community-level analyses, we also define an “any-rich” label: a node
 257 is rich if it belongs to the rich set under either seller- or buyer-richness at the given threshold.
 258 To summarize how concentrated rich nodes are within the community structure, we compute
 259 coverage curves $RC_{coverage}(k)$, defined as the cumulative fraction of rich nodes contained in
 260 the top- k communities under alternative community rankings (e.g., by size, total strength, or
 261 total value added). The formal definition of $RC_{coverage}(k)$ is provided in Appendix C.

262 3. Results

263 3.1 Community landscape across resolutions

264 We first examine how the community structure of the 578-node IRIO supra-network changes
 265 with the Leiden resolution parameter γ and assess cross-method stability using InfoMap. Table
 266 1 reports the Leiden consensus modularity and the number of communities for $\gamma \in [0.5, 3.0]$,
 267 along with the modularity of the InfoMap partition.

268 *Table 1 Number of communities and modularity Q for Leiden consensus partitions across resolution values (γ)*
 269 *and for the InfoMap partition (weighted, directed network).*

Community Detection		Communities	Q
Leiden	$\gamma = 0.5$	8	0.5815
	$\gamma = 1.0$	17	0.6258
	$\gamma = 1.5$	23	0.6248
	$\gamma = 2.0$	27	0.6251
	$\gamma = 2.5$	29	0.6233

	$\gamma = 3.0$	29	0.6227
InfoMap		33	0.6220

270

271 Analysis across multiple resolutions demonstrates that the Leiden algorithm consistently
 272 reveals a multiscale modular structure. At the coarsest setting $\gamma = 0.5$, the network divides into
 273 8 communities with modularity $Q = 0.5815$. Increasing the resolution parameter to $\gamma = 1.0$
 274 yields 17 communities and achieves the highest modularity observed in this analysis. Further
 275 increases in resolution produce progressively finer partitions, while modularity remains within
 276 a narrow range around $Q \approx 0.623$ – 0.626 . This pattern suggests the presence of a modularity
 277 plateau (Fortunato 2010): once the resolution parameter approaches 1, additional increases
 278 primarily subdivide existing modules rather than reveal new mesoscale structures. InfoMap
 279 detects 33 communities with modularity $Q = 0.6220$, a value comparable to the higher-
 280 resolution Leiden solutions and indicative of a similarly fine-grained mesoscale organization.

281 The agreement between Leiden and InfoMap, measured by variation of information (VI) and
 282 normalized mutual information (NMI), increases as γ increases (see Table 2). When $\gamma = 0.5$,
 283 NMI is 0.692 and VI is 1.649, which shows that the 8-community solution is much coarser than
 284 InfoMap’s 33-community partition. At $\gamma = 1.0$, the similarity is already high (NMI = 0.866,
 285 VI = 0.824), and for $\gamma \geq 2.0$ the partitions are almost the same.

286 *Table 2 Similarity between Leiden and InfoMap partitions across γ using variation of information (VI) and*
 287 *normalized mutual information (NMI)*

γ	VI	NMI
0.5	1.649	0.692
1.0	0.824	0.866
1.5	0.490	0.925

2.0	0.271	0.960
2.5	0.222	0.967
3.0	0.218	0.968

288

289 Based on these results, we use $\gamma = 1.0$ as the main scale for the rest of the paper. The $\gamma = 1.0$
290 partition gives a meso-scale breakdown with 17 communities, reaches peak modularity, and
291 already shows strong consistency with InfoMap.

292 3.2 Geographic vs functional communities

293 Figure 2 shows the matrix plot of community structure of Indonesia IRIO network at resolution
294 $\gamma = 1.0$. This study evaluates whether detected communities primarily reflect geographic
295 segmentation, such as province- or island-based blocs, or functional clustering, such as sector-
296 or value-chain-based structures. The analysis employs (i) quantitative alignment between
297 community labels and exogenous labels and (ii) qualitative inspection of community
298 composition and maps at specified resolutions.

299

300 *Figure 2 Community assignment matrix for the 578-node province-sector IRIO network (Leiden consensus, $\gamma = 1.0$). Columns*
 301 *are sectors (ID in Appendix A Table 8) and row are provinces (ID in Appendix A Table 7); cells are colored by community ID.*

302 3.2.1 Quantitative alignment with province, island, and sector labels

303 Table 3 shows the NMI and ARI values comparing community assignments with province,
 304 island, and sector labels. The alignment between communities and provinces is high and gets
 305 stronger with higher resolution. For example, at $\gamma = 0.5$, NMI is 0.658 and ARI is 0.222, and
 306 at $\gamma = 1.0$, these increase to NMI 0.730 and ARI 0.286. Island alignment is also strong at both
 307 resolutions, with NMI values of 0.594 and 0.574, and ARI values of 0.422 and 0.336. In
 308 contrast, alignment with sectors is very weak. For the 17-sector labeling, NMI is 0.015 and

309 0.026, and ARI is close to zero or slightly negative. The broader sector classification shows a
 310 similar trend. These results suggest that communities are mainly defined by geographic factors.

311 *Table 3 Alignment between communities and exogenous labels (province, island, sector, and five-sector*
 312 *classification) at $\gamma = 0.5$ and $\gamma = 1.0$, measured by NMI and ARI.*

γ	Metric	Province	Sector	Island	Classification
0.5	NMI	0.66	0.01	0.59	0.02
	ARI	0.22	-0.01	0.42	0.00
1.0	NMI	0.73	0.03	0.57	0.03
	ARI	0.29	-0.01	0.34	0.00

313

314 3.2.2 Spatial structure of communities

315 As shown in Figure 2, most province–sector nodes belonging to the same province cluster
 316 within the same community. Several of these form single-province communities, such as the
 317 provinces on Java (e.g., West Java, DKI Jakarta, Central Java, East Java, and DI Yogyakarta)
 318 as well as Nusa Tenggara Timur (NTT), West Kalimantan, and Gorontalo. Others encompass
 319 small groups of geographically adjacent provinces, including Bengkulu–West Sumatra,
 320 Banten–Lampung, Bali–West Nusa Tenggara (NTB), South Kalimantan–Central Kalimantan,
 321 and Maluku–North Maluku–Papua. This spatial pattern is evident in the provincial maps
 322 shaded by majority community (Figure 3), where communities generally form contiguous or
 323 nearly contiguous regions, and in the community–province heatmap (Appendix D, Figure 6).

324

325 *Figure 3 Province map colored by the majority community at $\gamma = 1.0$ (community with the largest share of province–sector*
 326 *nodes in each province. Color: communities ID).*

327 When communities are aggregated to the island level, the mesoscale partition at $\gamma = 1.0$
 328 (Appendix D, Figure 7) remains strongly anchored to island geography. Most communities are
 329 either single-island or island-dominated, consisting exclusively of nodes from Sumatra, Java,
 330 Kalimantan, Sulawesi, or Bali–Nusa Tenggara. Only a few cross-island communities appear,
 331 forming corridor-like linkages such as Java–Sumatra, Sumatra–Papua, Kalimantan–Sulawesi,
 332 and Maluku–Papua. These cross-island communities likely represent inter-island trade
 333 corridors connecting otherwise island-centered production systems rather than broad, multi-
 334 island functional regions.

335 3.2.3 Sectoral composition

336 Although geography plays a significant role, the identified communities do not exhibit much
 337 sectoral specialization. Figure 2 shows that sectoral profiles are similar across communities,
 338 which aligns with the near-zero correlation between community and sector labels in Table 3.
 339 In most cases, sectors within the same province are grouped into the same community,
 340 reflecting the dominance of intra-provincial connections. This is expected, as economic ties
 341 within provinces tend to be stronger than those across provinces due to shared geographic

342 proximity, historical dependencies, and administrative ties. As a result, communities are
343 spatially cohesive but multi-sector, indicating that Indonesia's production organization is
344 influenced more by regional clustering than by sectoral specialization.

345 However, communities are not specialized by the 17-sector labels while still differing
346 functionally in their value-added composition and external-strength interface. When we
347 aggregate node attributes using the five-sector classification, these functional differences
348 become clearer. We therefore describe each community using two indicators: value-added
349 share, which captures where economic output is generated, and external strength, which
350 captures which sectors connect communities through exchange (see Section 2.6.1).

351 Table 4 shows the main sectors for each indicator. The full breakdown of sectoral shares is in
352 Appendix E (Figure 8). Nationally, Trade–Transport–Finance (TTF) most often leads in value-
353 added, while Agriculture–Mining and Manufacturing–Utilities lead in only a few communities
354 (three and two, respectively). In contrast, external strength is split more evenly between TTF
355 and Manufacturing–Utilities. In six of the seventeen communities, the top sector for value-
356 added is different from the top sector for external strength, which highlights the difference
357 between where value is created and where inter-community exchange happens.

358 The differences are most noticeable in the five largest value-added communities. Jakarta
359 (Community 4) is an intermediation-led hub, with both value-added and external strength
360 focused on TTF. West Java (Community 5) and Central Java (Community 6) are more
361 manufacturing-oriented, as Manufacturing–Utilities lead in both areas. East Java (Community
362 9) has a balanced structure: value added is led by TTF (about 35%) and Manufacturing–Utilities
363 make up a strong share (about 29%), but external strength is mainly from Manufacturing–
364 Utilities. In Jambi–Bangka Belitung–Riau Islands–Riau–South Sumatra (Community 2), value
365 added comes from resources like Agriculture–Mining, while external strength is led by

366 Manufacturing–Utilities. This shows that even regions rich in resources connect to the national
 367 economy through manufacturing links.

368 In summary, Java-based communities have a TTF-focused intermediation center in Jakarta and
 369 manufacturing-driven production centers in West, Central, and East Java. By contrast,
 370 Sumatra’s main community relies on a resource-based economy, with manufacturing sectors
 371 helping to support external trade.

372 *Table 4 Leading sectors by (i) community value-added composition and (ii) cross-community external strength*
 373 *(computed from inter-community flows). Communities ordered by total community value added. CID: communities*
 374 *ID*

CID	Value Added		External strength	
	Dominant sector	share	Dominant sector	share
4	Trade Transport Finance	0.602	Trade Transport Finance	0.473
9	Trade Transport Finance	0.346	Manufacturing Utilities	0.486
5	Manufacturing Utilities	0.395	Manufacturing Utilities	0.610
2	Agriculture Mining	0.320	Manufacturing Utilities	0.442
6	Manufacturing Utilities	0.324	Manufacturing Utilities	0.473
3	Trade Transport Finance	0.400	Manufacturing Utilities	0.544
0	Trade Transport Finance	0.329	Manufacturing Utilities	0.374
7	Agriculture Mining	0.459	Manufacturing Utilities	0.413
14	Trade Transport Finance	0.331	Trade Transport Finance	0.315
10	Trade Transport Finance	0.498	Trade Transport Finance	0.502

13	Agriculture Mining	0.386	Manufacturing Utilities	0.302
1	Trade Transport Finance	0.387	Trade Transport Finance	0.322
16	Trade Transport Finance	0.387	Trade Transport Finance	0.397
12	Trade Transport Finance	0.385	Trade Transport Finance	0.396
8	Trade Transport Finance	0.494	Trade Transport Finance	0.507
11	Trade Transport Finance	0.358	Trade Transport Finance	0.372
15	Trade Transport Finance	0.374	Trade Transport Finance	0.418

375

376 3.3 Rich-club position in the community structure

377 This section examines whether rich province–sector nodes are mostly found in one community
378 or spread across several modules. Table 5 shows the size and distribution of the rich set (any-
379 rich definition) across communities at $\gamma = 1.0$. As the richness threshold becomes stricter, the
380 number of rich nodes drop sharply, going from 80 at the 90th percentile to 39 and then 7 at the
381 95th and 99th percentiles. At the same time, fewer communities have at least one rich node, and
382 the Herfindahl index increases, which means there is more concentration. These results show
383 that the most exclusive rich club is small and found in only a few communities, while lower
384 thresholds still include nodes from many provinces, islands, and sectors.

385 Table 5 Dispersion of rich nodes across communities, provinces, islands, and sectors at $\gamma = 1.0$ under the any-
 386 rich definition for thresholds 90th, 95th, 99th. Herfindahl index computed over the distribution of rich nodes across
 387 communities.

Richness label-threshold	Any-rich		
	90 th	95 th	99 th
Number of rich nodes	80	39	7
Number of provinces	16	10	5
Number of islands	5	4	2
Number of sectors	16	12	4
Number of sector classification	5	5	3
Number of communities	11	9	5
Herfindahl index (across communities)	0.145	0.172	0.225

388

389 Table 6 shows that this concentration is not random. Using the enrichment test in Section 2.6.2,
 390 only a small number of communities are significantly enriched with rich nodes across
 391 thresholds, while most communities show depletion or no significant enrichment. At the 90th-
 392 percentile threshold, the significantly enriched communities are mainly Java-based, anchored
 393 in Jakarta and the provinces of West, Central, and East Java. Community 2 (Sumatra: Jambi,
 394 Bangka-Belitung, Riau Islands, Riau, and South Sumatra) and Community 3 (Java–Sumatra:
 395 Banten and Lampung) contain more rich nodes than average, but their enrichment is not
 396 statistically significant, suggesting intermediate “mid-core” positions. Overall, the results

397 support a multi-core structure in which several central communities jointly constitute the rich
 398 national core rather than a single dominant super-community.

399 *Table 6 Community-level enrichment of rich nodes (any-rich) at $\gamma = 1.0$. For each community: rich-node share*
 400 *rc_c , enrichment index E_c , and FDR-adjusted one-sided enrichment p-value p_c^* for thresholds 90th, 95th, 99th.*

401 *Significance: *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$. CID= community id.*

CID	99 th			95 th			90 th		
	rc_c	E_c	p_c^*	rc_c	E_c	p_c^*	rc_c	E_c	p_c^*
0	0	—	1	0.059	-0.198	0.69	0.098	-0.497	0.864
1	0	—	1	0	—	1	0	—	1
2	0.012	-0.042	0.674	0.059	-0.198	0.707	0.141	0.029	0.524
3	0	—	1	0.029	-1.198	0.914	0.235	0.766	0.082
4	0.167	3.78***	0.001	0.556	3.042***	0	0.778	2.490***	0
5	0.059	2.28	0.189	0.353	2.387***	0	0.647	2.225***	0
6	0.063	2.368	0.179	0.25	1.890*	0.018	0.438	1.660**	0.003
7	0	—	1	0.038	-0.811	0.886	0.077	-0.847	0.949
8	0	—	1	0	—	1	0	—	1
9	0.056	2.198	0.2	0.389	2.527***	0	0.611	2.143***	0
10	0	—	1	0	—	1	0.029	-2.234	0.995
11	0	—	1	0	—	1	0	—	1
12	0	—	1	0	—	1	0	—	1
13	0	—	1	0	—	1	0.088	-0.65	0.875
14	0	—	1	0.015	-2.198	0.994	0.059	-1.234	0.992
15	0	—	1	0	—	1	0	—	1
16	0	—	1	0	—	1	0	—	1

402

403 Figure 4 shows this concentration pattern with coverage curves $RC_{coverage}(k)$. When
 404 communities are ranked by size, the cumulative share of rich nodes rises slowly, which means
 405 that the largest groups do not always have most of the rich nodes. However, if communities are
 406 ranked by total strength or total value added, the coverage grows much faster. This suggests
 407 that rich nodes are found mainly in economically strong communities, not just in the largest
 408 ones.

409
 410 *Figure 4 Concentration of rich nodes across communities at $\gamma = 1.0$ using the any-rich definition. (a) Coverage curves*
 411 *$RC_{coverage}(k)$ for rich thresholds 90th, 95th, 99th with communities ranked by size. (b) $RC_{coverage}(k)$ comparison*
 412 *under community rankings by size, total community strength, and total community value added.*

413 3.4 Community backbone

414 Figure 5 shows the minimum spanning tree (MST) backbone of the community network ($\gamma =$
 415 1.0), which highlights the main inter-community connections. The backbone forms a main
 416 corridor that links the Java core to Sumatra, Sulawesi, and Maluku on one side, and to
 417 Kalimantan and Bali–Nusa Tenggara on the other. Smaller communities are attached as
 418 peripheral leaves along this corridor. Node size represents total inter-community flow, node
 419 color indicates the proportion of rich nodes, and edge width corresponds to bilateral coupling
 420 strength.

421

422 *Figure 5 Minimum spanning tree (MST) backbone of the community network at $\gamma = 1.0$ (edges weighted by bilateral inter-*
 423 *community coupling). Node size represents total inter-community flow (in+out), node color shows rich-node share in the*
 424 *community, and edge width is proportional to bilateral coupling strength.*

425 The inter-community MST reveals a distinct core–satellite structure, aligning with evidence
 426 that input–output networks exhibit hierarchical organization and central cores (Cerina et al.
 427 2015), and with the core–periphery structure we previously reported for Indonesia’s
 428 intranational production network (Maulana et al. 2024). Java rich communities (e.g. Jakarta,
 429 West Java, Central Java, and East Java) are at the center, with large node sizes, many rich nodes,
 430 and occupy central positions in the MST backbone, highlighting their role as network hubs. In
 431 contrast, most communities in Kalimantan, Sulawesi, and eastern Indonesia are small
 432 peripheral nodes with few rich nodes, acting as satellites whose external connections mediated
 433 through the Java core. Within this core, Jakarta and East Java serve as strategic hubs. Jakarta
 434 connects Java to the west (Sumatra) and east (Sulawesi, Maluku, Papua), while East Java links
 435 to Kalimantan and Bali–Nusa Tenggara. Outside Java, Community 2 (South Sumatera, Jambi,

436 Riau, Riau Islands, Bangka Belitung) acts as a secondary hub, with higher inter-community
437 flow and more rich nodes than average.

438 The inter-community MST underscores the gateway role of Java's rich-core communities
439 because the strongest inter-community corridors run through the Java-centered core. The
440 backbone tree is organized around a small set of trunk links connecting the Java core to Sumatra
441 and to the eastern modules. As a result, the MST also highlights backbone bottlenecks since
442 removing these trunk links from the tree would separate the western (Sumatra), central
443 (Kalimantan, Bali, Nusa Tenggara), and eastern (Sulawesi, Maluku, Papua) components.

444 **4. Discussion**

445 Indonesia's intranational production network exhibits a modular structure that is strongly
446 shaped by geography. Community detection shows a clear spatial imprint. Most communities
447 align with neighboring provinces or island groupings, which is consistent with evidence from
448 other intranational MRIO settings (Wang et al. 2021). At the same time, these modules are not
449 narrowly specialized by sector labels. Instead, communities differ in how value added is
450 generated and in which sectors form their main interfaces to other communities. Taken together,
451 the results point to a hierarchically coordinated system in which regional blocks play distinct
452 economic roles within a geographically fragmented yet increasingly integrated archipelago.

453 Rich-club and enrichment analyses show that economic centrality is distributed across several
454 rich-core communities rather than concentrated in a single dominant module. This pattern is
455 consistent with a multicore-periphery organization in which multiple dense cores coexist
456 alongside a broader periphery (Yan and Luo 2019). Rich province-sector nodes concentrate in
457 a small number of economically central communities, particularly in Java, which form the
458 national rich core. Communities outside Java, especially in Sumatra, have above-average rich-
459 node presence but do not reach statistical significance, suggesting intermediate positions that

460 may function as secondary cores depending on the threshold. Similar concentration patterns
461 have been documented in global input–output networks, where a limited number of leading
462 country-centered communities concentrate connectivity and value added while other
463 communities occupy more peripheral roles (Cerina et al. 2015; del Rio-Chanona et al. 2017;
464 Kireyev et al. 2022). In Indonesia, the main Java communities are oriented toward trade,
465 transport, finance, and manufacturing. Sumatra’s intermediate communities are more resource-
466 based and connected through manufacturing linkages. This composition highlights how
467 multiple centers jointly shape national production integration.

468 Our approach to identifying rich-core communities differs from modularity-based core
469 detection in earlier IO-network studies. Cerina et al. (2015) and Zhu et al. (2014) identify cores
470 within communities by examining within-module contributions, thereby distinguishing central
471 from peripheral nodes within each module. In contrast, we identify which communities are
472 rich-core based on statistically significant over-representation of rich nodes. This shifts the
473 concept of “core” from the node level to the mesoscale. It also allows comparisons across
474 communities and clarifies which modules collectively constitute the national core.

475 The inter-community minimum spanning tree (MST) backbone clarifies how these core
476 communities connect the national system. The strongest corridors run through the Java-
477 centered core. They form a trunk that links Sumatra in the west with Kalimantan, Sulawesi,
478 and Maluku in the east, which supports inter-island production integration. Jakarta and East
479 Java play complementary roles within this corridor. Jakarta functions as an intermediation hub
480 between Western and Eastern modules. East Java serves as an industrial and logistical hub
481 linking Java to Kalimantan and the eastern islands. Peripheral areas in eastern Indonesia are
482 connected only through a few trunk links in the backbone. This indicates backbone bottlenecks
483 that could fragment the inter-community backbone and signal potential vulnerabilities in
484 national integration (Gomez et al. 2020). The co-location of rich nodes with these gateway

485 communities suggests that spatially uneven integration is a persistent feature of Indonesia's
486 production network.

487 The combination of spatial modularity, functional differentiation, and hierarchical
488 concentration shows how local production clusters and inter-island corridors interact in
489 Indonesia's economy. This setup brings efficiency benefits from agglomeration but also creates
490 risks due to dependence on key hubs, which matches theories of spatial inequality and network-
491 driven concentration (Baldwin and Philippe 2004; Hill 2008). The corridor centered on Java
492 helps connect regions but directs most value creation to the core, making regional opportunities
493 uneven. Although modular organization can help absorb local shocks, relying too much on a
494 few corridor links could weaken national resilience (Gomez et al. 2020; Giannakis et al. 2024).
495 Finally, there are some methodological limitations to consider. The MST summarizes the
496 strongest inter-community links and omits redundant routes by construction (Bhattacharjee and
497 Maiti 2025). The IRIO table also provides a static snapshot and does not capture adjustments
498 over time. Future research could build on this by using temporal IO data (Cerina et al. 2015)
499 or simulating shock propagation to see how resilient the system is during disruptions (Gomez
500 et al. 2020). Even with these limits, the mesoscale approach in this study provides a strong
501 foundation for understanding how geographic fragmentation, functional specialization, and
502 core concentration shape national production systems.

503 **5. Conclusion**

504 This study investigates the mesoscale organization of Indonesia's intranational production
505 network using the 2016 IRIO supra-network. We assess whether production communities are
506 shaped primarily by geography or function, examine how rich nodes distribute across
507 communities, and interpret what the inter-community backbone implies for national
508 integration.

509 The results show that Indonesia’s production system is organized into spatially grounded yet
 510 functionally differentiated communities. Community assignments align strongly with
 511 provincial and island boundaries rather than sectoral divisions, forming multi-sector regional
 512 blocs. Value creation and inter-community exchange diverge within these blocs because the
 513 sectors that generate value added are not always those that mediate cross-community
 514 connectivity. Rich nodes concentrate in a limited number of Java-centered communities, while
 515 Sumatra contains intermediate communities with elevated rich-node presence, supporting a
 516 polycentric hierarchy in economic centrality. The inter-community MST backbone highlights
 517 a Java-centered corridor linking western and eastern Indonesia through Jakarta and East Java,
 518 and it indicates potential backbone bottlenecks relevant to national integration.

519 Methodologically, the combination of consensus Leiden communities, rich-node enrichment,
 520 and inter-community backbone extraction provides a practical framework for intranational
 521 MRIO network analysis. Future work can extend this approach using time-varying IO data and
 522 explicit shock simulations to evaluate redundancy, rerouting capacity, and policy-relevant
 523 resilience under disruption.

524 6. Appendices

525 Appendix A. Provinces and Sectors

526 *Table 7 Province IDs and island/region groupings used in the 2016 IRIO network (BPS, 2021)*

Prov ID	Province	Region	Prov ID	Province	Region
11	Aceh	Sumatera	52	Nusa Tenggara Barat (NTB)	Bali Nusa
12	North Sumatera	Sumatera	53	Nusa Tenggara Timur (NTT)	Bali Nusa
13	West Sumatera	Sumatera	61	West Kalimantan	Kalimantan
14	Riau	Sumatera	62	Central Kalimantan	Kalimantan
15	Jambi	Sumatera	63	South Kalimantan	Kalimantan

16	South Sumatera	Sumatera	64	East Kalimantan	Kalimantan
17	Bengkulu	Sumatera	65	North Kalimantan	Kalimantan
18	Lampung	Sumatera	71	North Sulawesi	Sulawesi
19	Babel Island	Sumatera	72	Central Sulawesi	Sulawesi
21	Riau Island	Sumatera	73	South Sulawesi	Sulawesi
31	DKI Jakarta	Java	74	South East Sulawesi	Sulawesi
32	West Java	Java	75	Gorontalo	Sulawesi
33	Central Java	Java	76	West Sulawesi	Sulawesi
34	DI Yogyakarta	Java	81	Maluku	Maluku
35	East Java	Java	82	North Maluku	Maluku
36	Banten	Java	91	West Papua	Papua
51	Bali	Bali Nusa	94	Papua	Papua

527

528 *Table 8 Sector IDs and five-sector classification used in the 2016 IRIO network (BPS, 2021)*

Sector ID	Sector	Classification
1	Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries	Agriculture Mining
2	Mining and Quarrying	Agriculture Mining
3	Manufacture	Manufacturing Utilities
4	Electricity and Gas Supply	Manufacturing Utilities
5	Water Supply, Waste Management, Waste and Recycling	Manufacturing Utilities
6	Construction	Construction
7	Wholesale and Retail Trade, Car and Motorcycle Repair	Trade Transport Finance
8	Transportation and Warehousing	Trade Transport Finance

9	Accommodation and Food and Beverage Provision	Trade Transport Finance
10	Information and Communication	Trade Transport Finance
11	Financial and Insurance Services	Trade Transport Finance
12	Real Estate	Trade Transport Finance
13	Corporate Services	Trade Transport Finance
14	Government Administration, Defense, and Compulsory Social Security	Public Personal Services
15	Education Services	Public Personal Services
16	Health Services and Social Activities	Public Personal Services

529

530 **Appendix B. Implementation details for community detection**

531 We remove self-loops by setting diagonal weights to zero and use edge weights in all runs. We
532 run Leiden at $\gamma \in \{0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0\}$ with $R = 1000$ random initializations per γ ,
533 producing memberships $\{c_i^{(r)}\}$. We run InfoMap $R = 1000$ times (one optimization per run;
534 trials=1) on the same weighted, directed graph. For each method, we compute the co-
535 assignment matrix

$$536 \quad A_{ij} = \frac{1}{R} \sum_{r=1}^R \mathbf{1}\{c_i^{(r)} = c_j^{(r)}\} \quad (8)$$

537 then recluster A as a weighted, undirected similarity network (multilevel/Louvain-type) to
538 obtain a single consensus partition used in downstream analysis.

539 **Appendix C. Enrichment null model and coverage curves**

540 For a given threshold, let K be the number of rich nodes and N the total number of nodes. For
541 community c with n_c nodes and k_c rich nodes, under the hypergeometric null:

$$542 \quad P(K_c = k_c) = \frac{\binom{K}{k_c} \binom{N-K}{n_c - k_c}}{\binom{N}{n_c}} \quad (9)$$

543 We compute one-sided enrichment p-values

$$544 \quad p_c = P(K_c \geq k_c) = \sum_{x=k_c}^{\min(n_c, K)} P(K_c = x)$$

545 (10)

546 and apply Benjamini–Hochberg FDR correction. We classify a community as a rich-core

547 community if it exhibits over-representation of rich nodes, i.e., $E_c > 0$ and the FDR-adjusted

548 p_c is significant at conventional levels *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$. Coverage curves. Let

549 $|R|$ be the number of rich nodes and R_c the number of rich nodes in community c . For a

550 chosen ranking of communities, let Top- k be the first k communities. Define

$$551 \quad RC_{coverage}(k) = \frac{\sum_{c \in \text{Top-}k} R_c}{|R|}$$

552 (11)

553 Appendix D. community–province/island heatmap

554

555 *Figure 6 Heatmap of community-by-province composition at $\gamma = 1.0$ (rows: communities; columns: provinces;*

556 *entries: share of nodes, %).*

557

558 *Figure 7 Heatmap of community-by-island composition at $\gamma = 1.0$ (rows: communities; columns: islands; entries:*
 559 *share of nodes, %).*

560 **Appendix E. Community sector profiles**

561

562 *Figure 8 Community sector profiles at $\gamma = 1.0$: (a) value-added sector mix (five-sector classification) and (b)*
 563 *external-strength sector mix based on cross-community flows. Communities ordered by total community value*
 564 *added.*

565

566 **Abbreviations**

- ARI Adjusted Rand Index
- BPS Statistics Indonesia (*Badan Pusat Statistik*)
- CID Community ID
- DI *Daerah Istimewa* (Special Region; e.g., DI Yogyakarta)
- DKI *Daerah Khusus Ibukota* (Special Capital Region; DKI Jakarta)
- FDR False Discovery Rate (Benjamini–Hochberg procedure)
- ID Identifier (used for Province ID / Sector ID)
- IO Input–Output
- IRIO Interregional Input–Output

MRIO Multi-Regional Input–Output
MST Minimum Spanning Tree
NMI Normalized Mutual Information
NTB *Nusa Tenggara Barat* (West Nusa Tenggara)
NTT *Nusa Tenggara Timur* (East Nusa Tenggara)
TTF Trade–Transport–Finance (sector group)
VI Variation of Information
WIOD World Input–Output Database

567

568 **Author contributions**

569 Conceptualization: A.M. Methodology: A.M.,P.P.,A.F.A.,HS. Formal analysis:
570 A.M.,P.P.,A.F.A.,HS. Writing, review and editing: A.M.,P.P.,A.F.A.,HS. All authors have read
571 and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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575 **Data Availability**

576 The dataset supporting the conclusions of this article is(are) available in the GitHub repository,
577 <https://github.com/ardianeff/2016irioindonesia.git>.

578 **Declarations**

579 **Conflict of interest**

580 The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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